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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Desarrollo de las orientaciones de valores de la generación más joven: fomento de la responsabilidad social, la identidad cívica y una actitud de vida activa*

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Resumen. Un componente importante del trabajo social y la educación de las generaciones más jóvenes es el desarrollo de un programa para fomentar los valores espirituales y morales tradicionales. El estudio tuvo como objetivo identificar los efectos de la formación social en la juventud, en particular el desarrollo de la responsabilidad social, la identidad cívica y una actitud vital activa. El artículo presenta los resultados de una investigación teórica y empírica realizada en 2025. El estudio se llevó a cabo en las plataformas innovadoras del Instituto para el Estudio de la Infancia, la Familia y la Educación, con docentes que implementan el programa Orlyata Rossii y padres de los niños participantes. El método de investigación clave fue una encuesta. Los resultados del estudio establecen los efectos de la formación social de Orlyata Rossii, centrándose en el desarrollo de la actividad social como condición para la formación de la orientación valórica de los jóvenes en las organizaciones educativas. También se revelaron ciertas inconsistencias que reducen la eficacia del programa en la implementación práctica. No obstante, los elementos desarrollados y probados del programa pueden integrarse en otros programas de formación social para jóvenes. Estos elementos pueden promover el autoconocimiento y el desarrollo personal de los niños, su experiencia de participación

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en la vida pública del municipio, la región y el país, así como el desarrollo de la responsabilidad social, nuevos roles sociales y modelos de cooperación, y la formación de una perspectiva compartida sobre diversas situaciones de la vida.

Palabras clave: valores, organizaciones de educación general, escolares, docentes, padres.

Development of value orientations of the younger generation: fostering social responsibility, civic identity, and an active life stance

Abstract. An important component of social work and upbringing of the younger generation is the development of a program to foster traditional spiritual and moral values. This objective entails the need to find effective instruments to develop the value orientations of students in educational organizations. The study aimed to identify the social upbringing effects of the development of value orientations in youth, particularly the development of social responsibility, civic identity, and an active life stance. The paper reports the results of theoretical and empirical research conducted in 2025. The study was conducted at the innovative platforms of the Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family, and Education on teachers implementing the Orlyata Rossii program and the parents of participating children. The key research method was a questionnaire survey. The results of the study establish the social upbringing effects of Orlyata Rossii, targeting the development of social activity as a condition for building the value orientations of youth in educational organizations. Certain inconsistencies that reduce the program's effectiveness in practical implementation were also revealed. Notwithstanding, the developed and tested elements of the program can be integrated into other programs for the social upbringing of youth. These elements can promote the self-knowledge and self-development of children, their experience of participation in the public life of the municipality, region, and country, as well as the development of social responsibility, new social roles, and models of cooperation and the formation of a shared perspective of various life situations.

Keywords: values, general education organizations, schoolchildren, teachers, parents.

INTRODUCTION

The family and the education system traditionally play a key part in shaping the value orientations of younger generations (Hitlin & Piliavin, 2004; Khammatova et al., 2021; Agre et al., 2023; Letova, 2024). In regulatory documents governing the work of educational organizations, traditional spiritual and moral values are defined as an invariant component of social and upbringing work (Lykova et al., 2023; Shichkin et al., 2024). The transfer of values and their assimilation by students is the fundamental goal of social upbringing activities, the expected results of which may be different depending on the age stage (Vassilchenko, 2024; Rakimzhanova et al., 2025). These tasks raise the need to identify effective tools to develop the value orientations of students in educational organizations (Ukolova et al., 2024; Beskorovaynaya et al., 2025).

The purpose of this study was to identify the social upbringing effects of the development of value orientations in youth in general education organizations. Specifically, the focus of the research lay on the formation of social responsibility, civic identity, and an active life stance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the most productive mechanisms for the transition of social value to the category of personally significant value orientation is the upbringing process in educational organizations (Sheripova & Alieva, 2024; Maimerova et al., 2025). Hinging on the socially recognized and supported examples of pedagogical culture, cultural life, communication, the cultural image of a person, and proper behavior and activity, the upbringing process in educational organizations ensures the formation and development of the value-meaning sphere of the personality among students (Goloshumova et al., 2019). The content of the value-meaning sphere can be interpreted as the cognitive representation of, among other things, the satisfaction of communication interaction needs within interpersonal coordination and as part of group survival and well-being (Schwartz & Bilsky, 1987; Roccas & Sagiv, 2010; Pashkurov et al., 2023). The successful consolidation of the values broadcast by the teacher in children's value-meaning sphere and the development of their subjective significance are evidenced by several criteria. A model developed by Safiullina (2014) highlights the following criteria:

- 1) informational – the child's knowledge of values, meanings, and norms of interaction both with peers in particular and generally in human relationships and the functioning of society;
- 2) intellectual – the level of ability to analyze one's own and other people's actions and deeds in terms of compliance with the values adopted in society and the ability to determine the subjective significance of these values;
- 3) emotional-value – the ability to emotionally react to the surrounding reality in a positive way and emotionally-morally assess people's individual actions and deeds (including their own);
- 4) motivational – the child's awareness of subjective moral responsibility to the surrounding society and reality, as well as the expression of kindness, justice, and empathy towards others;
- 5) activity-instrumental – the child's ability to help others and choose relevant behavior options.

These criteria concord with the provisions of the Federal Working Program for Upbringing (FWPU) on the transfer of values in the process of upbringing. Specifically, the FWPU provides for informing students, providing them with knowledge about values (consistent with the information criterion in Safiullina's model), fostering their personal attitudes to these values (the emotional-value and motivational criteria), and creating conditions for students to accumulate experience acting in accordance with the obtained values, knowledge, and attitudes (the activity-instrumental criterion). A critical outcome of a child assimilating the translated values is reflection on its personal significance and willingness to integrate it into their personal value-meaning sphere (corresponds to the intellectual criterion) and regulate their behavior, communication, and activity on its basis from then on (Mikhaylova, 2024; Kurushkin & Polukhtina, 2025).

Solovtsova (2012) describes four stages of the assimilation of values as part of the upbringing situations created by the teacher: 1) preparatory, 2) value presentation, 3) disclosure of value content, 4) organization of substantive activities based on the assimilated value.

These stages of value assimilation underscore the role of the teacher, who exerts upbringing influence in the situation of the translation of values and their interiorization by students (Izotova, 2024; Sidorov, 2025). The professional responsibility of the teacher entails a qualitative distinctiveness of both the value translation process (purposeful, not situational and sporadic) and the content of the broadcast values (reflected upon and focused on concrete norms, attitudes, and ideals, rather than actualized by the subject's internal state and external factors) (Weran & Kuswandono, 2021). This role makes the teacher one of the key actors in the formation of the value orientations of schoolchildren (Akhmetshin et al., 2025). That being said, parents unequivocally retain the priority right to bring up their children as they see fit (Temerbayeva et al., 2023).

The conducted analysis of theoretical sources demonstrates that the value transfer process is multidimensional and multifactorial. At the same time, it leads us to conclude that the problem of developing the value orientations of schoolchildren is currently underdeveloped, and the conditions for the effectiveness of this process need to be studied closely.

METHODS

Study design and research subject

To achieve the set research goal, we focused on systematizing data on the detection of social upbringing potential. Comprehensive child upbringing can only be achieved through productive interaction between the faculty of an educational organization and parents, including as part of extracurricular activities. One example of such activities is the Orlyata Rossii program, which has been implemented in schools since 2021. According to the official website, the number of its participants has now reached 4 million students and 150 thousand teachers. Such a large-scale project can be considered a modern sociocultural phenomenon in the Russian educational space. Therefore, there is a need to explore its role in the development of value orientations among younger students. The present study uses the example of the Orlyata Rossii program, targeting its influence on students' personal and social development and the formation of peer groups in younger schoolchildren.

In our inquiry, we turned to research on the psychological and pedagogical aspects of the Orlyata Rossii program for the development of social activity of primary school students. The experience of its implementation in general education institutions was studied in 2025, relying on the works of Melnikova (2025), Bogumilchik (2025), Izotova (2024), and Pechkanova (2025), as well as the relevant experience of innovative platforms of the Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family, and Education.

The Orlyata Rossii program is designed to aid in the development of students' knowledge of social values relationships and experience of positive transformation of the social world based on traditional Russian spiritual and moral values. The program also seeks to foster a culture of communication and love for the Fatherland, its history, culture, and nature, as well as to nurture

independence and responsibility. The design of the program accounts for the characteristics of primary school age. At the beginning of this stage, the child is only beginning to gain serious social responsibilities in their transition from kindergarten to school. By the end of primary school age, having gone through the development of social activity, the child already has an activated subjective position and the desire to gain recognition from peers and be included in the reference group (Feldstein, 2009).

At its core, the Orlyata Rossii program is aimed at developing the civic activity, patriotism and social responsibility of primary school students; maintaining their interest in educational and extracurricular activities; and shaping a value attitude towards the Motherland, team, family, health, nature, and knowledge (Bogumilchik, 2025). These values are embedded in the content of the main areas of education for younger students, which prioritize the development of leadership, responsibility, collectivism, and patriotism, nurturing diligence, work, mercifulness, empathy, interest in knowledge, sports, and health, and personal environmental culture.

The work envisioned in the program's different tracks largely overlaps with the methodology of collective and creative activity developed by Ivanov (2021). Specifically, Ivanov's methodology involves the participation of younger students in the joint organization and implementation of educational events of various orientations (Buyanov & Lobyntseva, 2023; Pashkurov et al., 2023) and provides for the active involvement of students' parents in various roles (participants, hosts of individual tracks, specific events, etc.) (Nevzorova, 2023). The interaction of all subjects has to be built on cooperation, which is supported by collectively adopted rules (norms) of relations, by delegating real managerial powers to students, and by building an environment of mutual responsibility and mutual trust. This approach is consistent with the ideas of self-organization of children and adults in the education system, which we understand as

“The process of transformation of subjective uncertainty into certainty, as well as the spontaneous emergence of small informal societies (groups, associations, formations, communities, teams), the source of which is a factor impulse, the essence is effective joint interactions to overcome uncertainty, and the basis of existence is social interactions or interpersonal communication” (Evladova et al., 2020: 262).

The program is implemented as part of extracurricular activities. According to the Federal Educational Program for Primary General Education, extracurricular activities are an indispensable part of the basic educational program and are aimed at

“the achievement of the planned results of mastering the primary general education program, taking into account the extracurricular training courses chosen by the participants of educational relations from the list proposed by the educational organization and carried out in forms other than lessons” (Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, 2023).

Therefore, these activities need to harmoniously supplement the FWPU to provide a positive upbringing effect. Accordingly, the Orlyata Rossii program should be viewed as a resource for organizing a united upbringing space that will improve the effectiveness of FWPU implementation in primary school. This positive contribution stems from the fact that the Orlyata Rossii program is built on the same methodological approaches and principles as the FWPU, has similar goals and objectives, and targets the same values.

The upbringing effects of the program can be judged by the actualization of certain upbringing value orientations in students' behavior (Bardi & Schwartz, 2003) that reflect the basic constitutional and traditional spiritual and moral values of Russia. According to the axiological approach, this manifestation of values is the goal of upbringing and serves as an indicator of the transfer and assimilation of values specified in the targets of upbringing programs for each age stage.

Given that the program was launched in general education institutions relatively recently, its effectiveness in developing students' value orientations is not that well-researched. The present research is a pilot study focused on determining the positive social upbringing effects of the program that can serve as a basis for the primary study of its effectiveness.

Research stages and methods

The study was conducted at the innovative platforms of the Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family, and Education among teachers implementing the Orlyata Rossii program and the parents of participating children. The purpose of the survey was to study the attitude of these subjects to the Program and identify its advantages and disadvantages in terms of content, methodological equipment, and upbringing effects.

Accordingly, the primary research method at this stage was a questionnaire, which comprised several blocks of questions:

- assessment of the existing experience of upbringing practice related to the implementation of the program;
- the attitudes of teachers and parents to the Orlyata Rossii program;
- assessment of the level of satisfaction with the program and its methodological content among teachers;
- aspects of the influence of the program on students' development;
- identification of challenges and problems arising in the implementation of the program.

The study covered a total of 72 educational organizations. The choice in favor of the Institute's innovative research platforms was determined by a number of factors: direct involvement in the implementation of the program; the interest of administrators and teachers in improving the effectiveness of the program; organizational and management conditions allowing to optimize data collection and analysis (the availability of a coordinator from the Institute, work chats, updated contact databases, access to the necessary information resources (the Anketolog system), technical support specialists, etc.); and the ability to constructively and promptly revise research tools, if necessary.

In order to identify the upbringing effects of the program as one of the conditions for the development of value orientations in younger students in general education organizations, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of theoretical and program-methodological materials, which enabled us to establish and summarize the methodological foundations of the study. Through direct participation in the examination of materials submitted by applicants for the status of the Institute's innovation platform under the Orlyata Rossii program (videos demonstrating practi-

cal implementation, presentation materials, and methodological developments), a number of contradictions were discovered: inconsistency of real practice with the expected results stated in the program; inability to apply the tools and the wide range of proposed means and forms of work with younger students in real practice, which undermined the effectiveness of the program; and fragmented and episodic (often formal) involvement of students' parents, who are highlighted as key subjects in the goals and objectives of the program.

Consequently, the content of the study and its design consisted of the following stages: 1) the development of tools in accordance with the purpose of the study; 2) testing the tools and their subsequent refinement; 3) conducting an instructional webinar with the representatives of innovation platforms; 4) direct survey of teachers and students' parents; 5) processing and interpretation of the obtained results; 6) reporting study results.

The teacher survey involved the representatives of 25 regions of the Russian Federation. The majority of the sample came from Sverdlovsk and Voronezh Oblasts and Krasnodar Krai and lived mainly in urban settlements (75%).

The age of most teachers was from 45 to 60 years (43%) and from 30 to 45 years (34%). The proportion of participants under 30 years old was 16%, and people over 60 years old made up 7%.

The recruited teachers had fairly long work experience in general education: the majority had over 20 years of experience (38%), 26% – from 10 to 20 years, 19% – up to 10 years, and 17% – less than 3 years of teaching experience.

Most of the surveyed teachers (60%) described their educational organizations as flagships of the Orlyata Rossii social activity program. This means that they believed their schools to be committed to providing methodological support to teachers from other educational organizations in their region to effectively master the program methodology, study, and exchange experience.

Of the surveyed teachers, 89% had experience participating in the program, with the majority (36%) having been involved for one year, 31% – for two years, 16% – for three years, and 6% – for 4 years. A total of 11% of the teachers did not have such experience.

The parents participating in the survey represented 30 regions of the Russian Federation, the majority being from Sverdlovsk, Voronezh, Nizhny Novgorod, Novosibirsk, Saratov, Sverdlovsk Oblasts, and Krasnodar Krai and predominantly residing in urban settlements (86%).

Most of the respondents representing the parent community were aged from 30 to 45 years old (82%), the share of participants from 45 to 60 years old was 13%, up to 30 years old – 5%, and over 60 years old – less than 1%.

RESULTS

One of the key objectives of the study was to compare the ideas of teachers and parents about the value orientations the program is designed to develop. The conducted research suggests no cardinal contradictions and discrepancies in the perception of the Program's value orientations among these subjects of education. Importantly, this question allowed multiple choice.

Most teachers suggested that children's participation in the program contributes to the development of patriotism (94%) and collectivism (78%) and develops the values of historical memory (74%) and the family (73%). On the other hand, the parents of primary school students pointed out the values of "patriotism" (76%), "mutual assistance and respect" (57%), and "collectivism" (54%). The distribution of responses is detailed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Teachers' and parents' perceptions of the program's value-based content.

Values (President of the Russian Federation, 2022)	Teachers	Parents
life	53%	36%
dignity	54%	34%
human rights and freedoms	47%	25%
patriotism	94%	76%
civic consciousness	70%	37%
devotion to the Fatherland and responsibility for its fate	62%	32%
high moral ideals	60%	36%
close-knit family	73%	42%
constructive labor	59%	28%
priority of the spiritual over the material	40%	18%
humanism	46%	23%
mercifulness	68%	38%
justice	59%	45%
collectivism	78%	54%
mutual assistance and respect	70%	57%
historical memory and generational continuity	74%	43%
unity of the peoples of Russia	57%	47%

Source: developed by the authors.

The results show that the differences between teachers' and parents' ideas about the educational potential of the Orlyata Rossii program in terms of developing students' value orientations are insignificant. Both teachers and parents noted the effects consistent with the Program's upbringing priorities. In percentage terms, however, the answers of teachers significantly surpass those of parents.

Considering that the Orlyata Rossii program focuses especially closely on fostering collectivism, our study placed a separate emphasis on this aspect. The results reveal that 89% of the teachers argued that the program affects the development of students' value attitudes towards peer groups, yet 10% of respondents considered this influence insignificant, and 1% saw no influence. At the same time, 80% of the teachers noted that relations in the peer group became more productive as a result of work under the Orlyata Rossii program, 20% found it difficult to answer this question, and less than 1% of teachers answered negatively. Detailing the changes, the teachers reported the following:

- * the children have become more united – 75%;
- * the children are actively involved in class/school activities –73%;
- * the children help one another – 72%;
- * the children show initiative – 65%;
- * the children participate in volunteer campaigns and projects – 62%;
- * the emotional climate in the class has become more favorable – 59%;
- * the children help each other in lessons – 40%.

Nevertheless, the teachers also highlighted some negative phenomena in their students that they believed to be associated with participation in the Orlyata Rossii program:

- * overload from activities – 12%;
- * competition in the class –11%;
- * the appearance of destructive leaders – 6%;
- * reduced interest in learning – 5%.

On their part, most parents (67%) suggested that participation in the Orlyata Rossii program helped their children significantly improve relationships with peers and friends, 21% believed that it helped slightly, and 9% argued that there was no positive effect.

Considering the social upbringing effects of the program, teachers noted positive changes in the communication (60%), cognitive (27%), and emotional (13%) spheres of primary school-children.

The most popular reasons determining these changes cited by teachers are the role of collective creative activities (their influence was indicated by 85% of teachers), the development of children's initiative (74%), mentoring, and responsibility for the decisions made (60% each). Just over half of survey participants (56%) also noted the role of joint planning. The importance of children's self-government was stressed by 43% of teachers, and joint case analysis was mentioned by 40%.

Parents noted an improvement in children's communication (49%) and an increase in the level of responsibility (48%) and organization (41%) after the inclusion of their children in the Orlyata Rossii program.

Among other things, the program provides for the active participation of schoolchildren in the design, development, implementation, and subsequent analysis of educational activities of various orientations following the methodology of collective creative activity. This provision is reflected in the answers of teachers. The most significant condition in the Orlyata Rossii program affecting the development of children's peer groups, according to teachers, is collective creative affairs (93%) (Figure 1). Great importance was also attached to supporting children's initiatives and independence, which was noted by 75% of respondents. The content laid down in the tracks of the program was highlighted as important by 58%. Half of the respondents also considered the participation of mentors from the Russian Movement of Children and Youth, the Movement of the First, to be an important condition for the formation of children's peer groups, and 35% referred to clearly defined scenarios and instructions.

FIGURE 1. Factors influencing the development of peer groups.

Source: Developed by the authors.

The Orlyata Rossii program actively involves students' parents in its implementation. In this context, an interesting fact was revealed – only 2% of teachers noted the involvement of parents as participants in the Program, while 45% of parents of students reported taking part in the Orlyata Rossii program in the following capacities:

- * supporting (specifics not clarified) and encouraging the child participating in the program;
- * helping the child progress through the program tracks;
- * helping the child in the preparation of creative works;
- * assisting the class teacher in implementing the program tracks.

One of the objectives of extracurricular activities is to support the initiatives of schoolchildren and the development of their self-organization, thus contributing to the development of initiative and leadership qualities, and the formation of self-government in the peer group. This implies a gradual transformation of students' position in joint activities from participants to co-organizers, which is confirmed by survey results.

Thus, the majority of teachers (63%) suggested that schoolchildren had demonstrated active participation in joint affairs, 21% of teachers noted children's participation as co-authors of class activities, and 13% asserted that children had realized themselves as project authors and organizers. In this context, a certain pattern can be observed: children in grades 1-2 acted mainly as participants in class events, mastering the methods of constructive interaction with each other, the ability to set individual and collective goals, and acting independently to achieve them; in

3rd grade, students became co-authors; in 4th grade, schoolchildren began to take on the roles of authors and organizers of class life.

In the 2024-25 school year, the Orlyata Rossii program became the first stage in the inclusion of children in the Movement of the First. Our study shows that teachers, much like students' parents, generally highly appreciate the role of children's and youth public associations in the development of value orientations in modern children, with 71% of teachers and 70% of parents noting a positive influence. Interestingly, 68% of the surveyed teachers used to be members of public organizations themselves: 50% of the teachers were Little Octobrists, 52% were members of pioneer organizations, and 29% were members of the Komsomol. On the other hand, 55% of the surveyed parents had never been part of public organizations. Of those who had, 26% were Little Octobrists, 21% were in a pioneer organization, and 4% were members of the Komsomol. The majority of respondents who had been involved in public organizations (93%) evaluated this life experience as good or very good (12% and 81%, respectively), while 5% described it as negative. The results give grounds to hypothesize that the subjective experience of teachers and parents can be projected both in a positive and negative way on their activities in the implementation of the Orlyata Rossii program.

In general, both teachers and parents have a positive perception of the impact of the Orlyata Rossii program on children. As many as 88% of teachers and 78% of parents agreed that the children enjoyed participating in the program.

DISCUSSION

The results of the theoretical and empirical stages of our study made it possible to substantiate the need for a comprehensive and systematic research of the problem of developing the value orientations of students in general education organizations as part of solving the strategic tasks of education at the current stage in the development of Russian education, in which spiritual and moral values have become an invariant component.

The analysis of educational programs demonstrates the high upbringing potential of the Orlyata Rossii program, implemented as part of extracurricular activities. The program provides an important tool for the upbringing of younger students, fostering their civic consciousness, collectivism, and responsibility to society.

This conclusion is supported by the teachers and the parents who took part in the study. Furthermore, the Orlyata Rossii program for the development of social activity gives schoolchildren the opportunity to prove themselves as active participants, co-authors of class activities, and the authors and organizers of various projects and events, which confirms the high engagement and interest of younger students (Mukhametkairov et al., 2024).

These findings are corroborated by other studies on certain aspects of the implementation of the Orlyata Rossii program. For example, Izotova (2024) investigated the attitudes of teachers to the program Orlyata Rossii among primary school teachers and advisers to directors of education. The survey covered 1984 respondents, about 90% of whom were involved in the Orlyata Rossii program. More than 90% of the respondents agreed that the Orlyata Rossii program

should be implemented in primary school because of its positive effect on elementary school students, including the development of qualities consistent with the targets of upbringing.

The effectiveness of the Orlyata Rossii program for the development of communicative universal learning actions in 2nd-grade students is confirmed by the results of an experiment conducted by Uchaikina (2023). In this study, the experimental group participating in the Orlyata Rossii program showed a 10% increase in students with a high level of communicative universal learning actions, with a 27% decrease in the low level. In addition, there was a significant increase in the number of experimental group students with a high level of the ability to express their point of view and argue their position. The indicator of the ability to find compromises and coordinate actions with partners also rose in the experimental group.

Nevertheless, the study identified certain contradictions that undermine the practical effectiveness of the Orlyata Rossii program in shaping the value orientations of students. The results point to the lack of comprehensive program and methodological solutions and the need to provide scientific and methodological support for the implementation of the program, accounting for the regional, sociocultural, and ethnocultural features of upbringing activities in general educational organizations.

Since the program has been integrated into the activities of the Movement of the First in 2024, its upbringing potential has expanded significantly, providing students with conditions for:

- * self-knowledge and self-development;
- * the realization of the rights of participation in the public life of the municipality, the region, and the country as a whole;
- * the intensification of initiative and independence;
- * socialization in an informal setting, mastering new social roles and models of cooperation, and developing a shared view of various life situations;
- * the development of social responsibility, civic identity, and an active life stance.

CONCLUSIONS

The research findings indicate a positive effect of participation in the Orlyata Rossii program in terms of the development of students' value orientations according to the subjective perceptions of both teachers implementing the program and the parents of participating students. Therefore, there is great potential in further empirical study of the effectiveness of the program as a mechanism for developing the value orientations of schoolchildren.

The significance of the conducted study lies in the opportunity to apply its results in other programs aimed at forming the values of the younger generation. In particular, the obtained findings make it possible to evaluate the potential of the program and its relevance to the upbringing activities of educational organizations as part of implementing the Federal Educational Program for Primary General Education and in improving the effectiveness of social upbringing activities designed by general educational organizations.

Further investigation of this topic will be instrumental for the development of comprehensive program and methodological solutions for establishing the mechanisms of continuity of social upbringing work between different levels of general education. In addition, continued research will make it possible to effectively integrate the experience of the Orlyata Rossii program into the activities of children's and youth public associations.

Contribution of the authors

The authors contributed equally to collecting empirical data, processing data, and writing the article.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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